

Additional File 5. The TCR-Vβ repertoire of T₁₀ cells is similar to that of the starting CD4⁺ T cells

Percentages of Vβ usage in T₁₀ cells (■) and in the corresponding CD4⁺ T cells before culture (□) are shown. Bars represent mean value of each dataset ± SD (n=5 T₁₀-cell preparations)